

**INFLUENCE OF Zn CONCENTRATION ON THE PROPERTIES OF La₂O₃
NANOSTRUCTURES**

S. Karthikeyan, M.Selvapandiyan*

Department of Physics, Periyar University PG Extension Centre, Dharmapuri 636701

ABSTRACT

Lanthanum oxide (La₂O₃) nanoparticles were synthesized by a simple sol gel method. Lanthanum nitrate, Zinc nitrate, Citric acid and double distilled water are used as starting materials. The samples with different Zn concentrations namely 0.1 and 0.2 mol were prepared with a reaction time of 3 & 6 hrs. The samples were calcinated at a temperature of 500°C for 2 hour. The as-prepared and calcinated samples have been subjected to various characterizations. The phase and structure of the samples have been identified by using X-ray diffraction. The morphology of the synthesized particles has been investigated by a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The SEM images of equal concentration samples (0.01 mol) show spherical structures. The FTIR spectra show the presence of different functional group present in the synthesized Nanoparticles. The absorbance spectra have been recorded in the UV-Visible region and analyzed.

Key words: La₂O₃:Zn; Band gap; SEM

*Corresponding author: Dr. M. Selvapandiyan ([mselvapandiyan@rediffmail.com](mailto:m Selvapandiyan@rediffmail.com))